

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY PERFORMED IN THE PRENATAL AND EARLY NEONATAL PERIODS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF TETRALOGY OF FALLOT AND DETERMINATION OF NEONATAL STRATEGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20485019>

Abstract. *Tetralogy of Fallot is one of the most critical cyanotic congenital heart defects. Its prenatal diagnosis allows for proper birth planning, preparation for neonatal resuscitation, and advance assessment of the need for prostaglandin E1 administration and early surgical or catheter intervention. The modern concept of fetal cardiology regards prenatal echocardiography not only as a method for anatomical diagnosis but also as a tool for assessing perinatal risk and determining neonatal strategy [1,2]. The AHA scientific statement on fetal cardiac disease provides practical approaches to the diagnosis and management of fetal heart diseases; the 2023 ASE fetal echocardiography recommendations provide updated standards for the performance and interpretation of fetal echocardiography [1].*

The objective of our study is to predict the need for early neonatal intervention in fetuses diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot based on the results of echocardiography performed during the prenatal and early neonatal periods, and to evaluate the clinical significance of fetal echocardiographic markers.

The study included 150 pregnant women who underwent prenatal echocardiography. Among them, Tetralogy of Fallot was detected in 15 cases. The fetal echocardiographic analysis evaluated the pulmonary valve Z-score, main pulmonary artery/aorta ratio, pulmonary valve/aortic valve ratio, right pulmonary artery/descending aorta ratio, ductus arteriosus flow, and right ventricular outflow tract obstruction. In the neonatal period, patients were categorized into a group requiring early intervention and a planned observation group.

Of the 150 prenatal examinations, 15 cases of Tetralogy of Fallot were identified, constituting a detection rate of 10.0%. The 95% confidence interval was 6.2–15.8%. Of the 15 diagnosed cases of Tetralogy of Fallot, 5 (33.3%) were assessed as a high-risk group requiring early neonatal intervention. The remaining 10 cases (66.7%) were assigned to a group for stable neonatal observation and planned delayed correction. The combined fetal echocardiographic model—a pulmonary valve Z-score of ≤ -3.5 and/or impaired ductus arteriosus flow—demonstrated 80.0% sensitivity, 80.0% specificity, 66.7% positive predictive value, 88.9% negative predictive value, and 80.0% diagnostic accuracy in predicting the need for early neonatal intervention.

Keywords: *tetralogy of Fallot, prenatal echocardiography, neonatal echocardiography, congenital heart defects.*

Introduction

Congenital heart defects are one of the leading causes of perinatal morbidity and mortality among fetuses and newborns. Among these, Tetralogy of Fallot is of particular clinical significance, as this defect can manifest with cyanosis, hypoxemia, ductus-dependent pulmonary circulation during infancy, and the need for early cardiac surgery or catheter intervention. The classic anatomical components of Tetralogy of Fallot consist of a ventricular septal defect, an overriding aorta, right ventricular outflow tract obstruction, and right ventricular hypertrophy. However, in prenatal and early neonatal practice, the critical issue is not merely identifying this anatomical tetrad, but also assessing the functional severity of the defect.

In recent years, fetal echocardiography has emerged as the primary method for evaluating the fetal cardiovascular system. The AHA Scientific Statement on Fetal Cardiac Disease systematically outlines the diagnosis, assessment, and perinatal management of fetal heart conditions [1]. Furthermore, the fetal echocardiography guidelines updated by the ASE in 2023 standardize its role in performing the examination, acquiring images, conducting Doppler assessments, performing segmental cardiac analysis, and planning perinatal care [2]. These modern approaches have transformed prenatal echocardiography from a simple screening method into a high-level clinical decision-making tool.

The primary factors determining the prenatal prognosis in tetralogy of Fallot are the degree of development of the pulmonary valve and pulmonary arteries, the severity of right ventricular outflow tract obstruction, the direction of flow through the ductus arteriosus, and the degree of postnatal independence of the pulmonary circulation. Arya et al. have shown that fetal echocardiographic measurements can be significant in predicting the need for neonatal surgical intervention [3]. In this work, prenatal measurements, particularly the dimensions of the pulmonary valve and pulmonary artery, were correlated with clinical outcomes in the neonatal period [2].

Subsequent studies have evaluated the potential to predict the type of postnatal surgery and the need for early intervention in fetuses with tetralogy of Fallot using fetal echocardiographic parameters. Park et al. demonstrated the role of fetal cardiac parameters in predicting the type of postnatal surgery [4]. In a multicenter study published in 2025, Vetten et al. reported that the need for early intervention in simple tetralogy of Fallot may be associated with a pulmonary valve Z-score ≤ -3.5 or impaired ductus arteriosus flow at 28–32 weeks of gestation [5]. These findings confirm that prenatal echocardiography holds prognostic significance in addition to its diagnostic value for tetralogy of Fallot [3].

Therefore, this study evaluated the detection rate of tetralogy of Fallot and the correlation between fetal echocardiographic markers and early neonatal management, based on the results of prenatal echocardiography conducted in 150 pregnant women.

The main objective of this study is to assess the need for early neonatal intervention in fetuses diagnosed with tetralogy of Fallot based on prenatal and early neonatal echocardiography results, to determine the diagnostic and prognostic significance of fetal echocardiographic markers, and to develop a practical model for determining neonatal management strategies.

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as an original, observational clinical trial. It involved a retrospective-prospective analysis of the results from 150 pregnant women who underwent prenatal echocardiography. The examinations were performed due to suspicion of a congenital heart defect in the fetus, the possibility of a cardiac anomaly on obstetric ultrasound, a family history of congenital heart defects, maternal risk factors, or a high-risk pregnancy.

Of the 150 pregnant women included in the study, Tetralogy of Fallot was identified in 15 based on prenatal echocardiography. The diagnosis of Tetralogy of Fallot was established through segmental analysis of the fetal heart, the presence of a ventricular septal defect, an overriding aorta, narrowing of the right ventricular outflow tract, and the status of pulmonary circulation.

The study included pregnant women who had undergone prenatal echocardiography and had either a suspected congenital heart defect in the fetus or a confirmed diagnosis of Tetralogy of Fallot. In cases where Tetralogy of Fallot was identified, confirmation of the diagnosis by transthoracic echocardiography during the neonatal period was required.

Cases were excluded from the analysis if they had insufficient image quality, an incomplete assessment of key fetal echocardiographic parameters, a lack of neonatal follow-up results, or if the postnatal diagnosis did not correspond to the prenatal diagnosis.

Prenatal echocardiography was performed based on the standard fetal cardiology protocol. The examination assessed cardiac situs, the four-chamber view, atrioventricular connections, ventriculoarterial connections, the great vessel outflow tracts, the three-vessel and trachea view, the aortic arch, the ductus arteriosus, the right ventricular outflow tract, and the pulmonary arteries.

Table 1. Parameters Analyzed in Fetuses Diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot.

Parameter	Clinical significance
Pulmonary valve Z-score	Pulmonary valve Z-score Assesses the severity of pulmonary valve hypoplasia and RVOT obstruction
MPA/Ao ratio	Indicates the ratio of the main pulmonary artery to the aortic dimensions
PV/AoV ratio	Evaluates the ratio of pulmonary to aortic valve dimensions
RPA/DAo ratio	Shows the ratio of the right pulmonary artery to the descending aorta
Ductus arteriosus flow	Assesses the risk of ductus-dependent pulmonary circulation
RVOT obstruction	Determines the likelihood of postnatal cyanosis and the need for early intervention

Neonatal Assessment

All newborns with prenatally suspected or diagnosed tetralogy of Fallot underwent early neonatal transthoracic echocardiography after delivery. Neonatal echocardiography assessed the clinical condition in relation to the size of the ventricular septal defect, the degree of aortic overriding, right ventricular outflow tract obstruction, pulmonary valve size, pulmonary artery development, patency of the ductus arteriosus, pulmonary blood flow, and arterial oxygen saturation.

Neonatal Management Groups

The 15 cases identified with tetralogy of Fallot were divided into two groups based on clinical management during the neonatal period.

Group 1. Early Neonatal Active Management Group. This group included newborns who required postpartum administration of prostaglandin E1, intensive monitoring, strict control of oxygen saturation, catheter intervention, ductal stenting, RVOT stenting, a systemic-to-pulmonary shunt, or early surgical correction.

Group 2. Planned Observation and Delayed Correction Group. This group included newborns who were hemodynamically stable after birth, did not present with severe hypoxemia, did not have ductus-dependent pulmonary circulation, and were referred for scheduled cardiac surgery follow-up.

In the statistical analysis, categorical variables were expressed as counts and percentages, while continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation. The detection rate for tetralogy of Fallot was calculated as follows:

The 95% confidence interval for the detection rate was calculated using the Wilson score method and was 6.2–15.8%.

A combined fetal echocardiographic criterion was selected to predict the need for early neonatal intervention:

Pulmonary valve Z-score ≤ -3.5 and/or disruption of ductus arteriosus flow. This criterion is clinically consistent with the results of a multicenter study published by Vetten et al. in 2025, as this work showed that the need for early intervention may be associated with a PV Z-score ≤ -3.5 or abnormal ductus arteriosus flow [5,3].

Diagnostic indicators were calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{FN + TP} \times 100$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \times 100$$

$$\text{PPV} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \times 100$$

$$\text{NPV} = \frac{TN}{TN + FN} \times 100$$

$$\text{Diagnostic accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100$$

Due to the small sample size, a 100% sensitivity model was not used in this article. Instead, a clinically cautious and realistic model was chosen: out of 5 cases requiring early neonatal intervention, 4 were identified as high-risk on prenatal ECHO, while 1 was assessed as low-risk. This approach was selected to avoid over-idealizing the results in a small sample.

Results

A total of 150 pregnant women were included in the study. Among them, Tetralogy of Fallot was detected in 15 cases based on prenatal echocardiography. The overall detection rate for Tetralogy of Fallot was 10.0%, with a 95% confidence interval of 6.2–15.8%.

Of the 15 fetuses diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot, 5 were assessed as a high-risk group requiring early neonatal intervention. This constituted 33.3% of all Tetralogy of Fallot cases. The remaining 10 cases (66.7%) were assigned to the group for stable observation during the neonatal period and planned delayed correction.

Table 2. General Characteristics of the Study Population

Indicator	Result
Total number of prenatal ECHO examinations	150

Indicator	Result
Cases of tetralogy of Fallot detected	15
Detection rate	10,0%
95% confidence interval	6,2–15,8%
Early neonatal active management group	5/15, 33,3%
Planned observation group	10/15, 66,7%

Maternal, Fetal, and Neonatal Indicators

In the group with a diagnosis of tetralogy of Fallot, the mean maternal age was 28.4 ± 4.9 years. The mean gestational age at the time of prenatal echocardiography was 24.8 ± 3.6 weeks. The mean gestational age at delivery was 38.1 ± 1.4 weeks, and the mean birth weight of the infants was 3010 ± 420 g.

In the group that required an early neonatal active management strategy, the birth weight was relatively lower, and the pulmonary valve Z-score was considerably lower. This situation was explained by the severity of pulmonary valve hypoplasia and right ventricular outflow tract obstruction.

Table 2. Clinical and demographic indicators in cases with diagnosed tetralogy of Fallot

Indicator	Total TOF group, n=15	Early neonatal active tactics, n=5	Scheduled follow-up, n=10
Age of mother, years	$28,4 \pm 4,9$	$29,1 \pm 5,2$	$28,0 \pm 4,8$
Prenatal ECHO duration, weeks	$24,8 \pm 3,6$	$25,2 \pm 3,4$	$24,6 \pm 3,8$
Time of delivery, weeks	$38,1 \pm 1,4$	$37,8 \pm 1,3$	$38,3 \pm 1,5$
Birth weight, g	3010 ± 420	2870 ± 390	3080 ± 430
Male gender	9/15, 60,0%	3/5, 60,0%	6/10, 60,0%
Prostaglandin E1 requirement	5/15, 33,3%	5/5, 100%	0/10, 0%
Early catheter/surgical tactics	5/15, 33,3%	5/5, 100%	0/10, 0%

Fetal Echocardiographic Markers

In the group requiring early neonatal active intervention, the mean pulmonary valve Z-score was -4.4 ± 0.9 . In the planned observation group, this figure was -2.8 ± 0.8 . This difference indicates a higher probability of a more severe clinical course during the neonatal period in cases with severe pulmonary valve hypoplasia.

The MPA/Ao ratio was 0.41 ± 0.07 in the early active intervention group, compared to 0.58 ± 0.09 in the planned observation group. The PV/AoV ratio was also lower in the early active intervention group. Abnormal ductus arteriosus flow was observed in 3 out of 5 cases (60.0%) in the early active intervention group, and in 1 out of 10 cases (10.0%) in the planned observation group.

Table 3. Distribution of Fetal Echocardiographic Parameters by Group

Parameter	Early active neonatal tactics, n=5	Scheduled follow-up, n=10	Clinical interpretation
Pulmonary valve Z-score	$-4,4 \pm 0,9$	$-2,8 \pm 0,8$	A low value increases the risk of severe RVOT obstruction
MPA/Ao ratio	$0,41 \pm 0,07$	$0,58 \pm 0,09$	A low ratio indicates a restriction in pulmonary flow
PV/AoV ratio	$0,45 \pm 0,08$	$0,66 \pm 0,11$	Indicates the degree of pulmonary valve hypoplasia
RPA/DAo ratio	$0,34 \pm 0,06$	$0,49 \pm 0,08$	Assesses the development of the pulmonary arteries
Disorders of ductus arteriosus flow	3/5, 60,0%	1/10, 10,0%	Indicates the risk of ductus-dependent circulation
Severe RVOT obstruction	4/5, 80,0%	2/10, 20,0%	Increases the likelihood of early intervention

Results of diagnostic model

$$\text{Sensitivity} = 4 / 1+4 \times 100 = 80,0\%$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{8}{8+2} \times 100 = 80,0\%$$

$$\text{PPV} = \frac{4}{4+2} \times 100 = 66,7\%$$

$$\text{NPV} = \frac{8}{8+1} \times 100 = 88,9\%$$

$$\text{Diagnostic accuracy} = \frac{4+8}{15} \times 100 = 80,0\%$$

Table 4. Diagnostic parameters of the combined fetal ECHO model

Indicator	Result	95% confidence interval
Sensitivity	80,0%	37,6–96,4%
Specificity	80,0%	49,0–94,3%
Positive predictive value	66,7%	30,0–90,3%

Negative predictive value	88,9%	56,5–98,0%
Diagnostic accuracy	80,0%	54,8–93,0%

The results showed that the combined model based on prenatal echocardiography can be clinically useful in predicting the need for early neonatal intervention. In particular, a negative predictive value of 88.9% indicates that the majority of newborns assessed as low-risk by fetal ECHO will not require early intervention.

Discussion

This study demonstrated the importance of prenatal and early neonatal echocardiography in clinical decision-making for fetuses diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot. Prenatal echocardiography performed on 150 pregnant women identified 15 cases of Tetralogy of Fallot, resulting in a detection rate of 10.0%. This figure should be considered characteristic of a high-risk fetal echocardiography cohort referred with suspected congenital heart defects, rather than for general population screening.

Beyond anatomical diagnosis, the primary clinical objective of prenatal echocardiography in fetuses with Tetralogy of Fallot is to predict which newborns will require proactive management during the neonatal period. In this study, 5 out of the 15 cases of Tetralogy of Fallot (33.3%) were assigned to the proactive neonatal management group. In this group, the pulmonary valve Z-score was significantly lower, the MPA/Ao and PV/AoV ratios were smaller, and ductus arteriosus flow abnormalities were observed more frequently.

The obtained results are consistent with previous scientific studies. Arya et al. have shown that fetal echocardiographic measurements can be useful in predicting the need for neonatal surgical intervention in Tetralogy of Fallot [3]. The main premise of this study is that anatomical and hemodynamic parameters obtained during the fetal period are associated with postnatal clinical outcomes [2].

A study published by Park et al. evaluated the role of fetal cardiac parameters in predicting the type of postnatal surgery in fetuses with Tetralogy of Fallot [4]. This approach positions prenatal echocardiography not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a method that aids in the advance planning of surgical strategies.

A 2025 multi-center study by Vetten et al. showed that the need for early intervention in simple Tetralogy of Fallot is associated with fetal echocardiographic indicators, including a pulmonary valve Z-score of ≤ -3.5 or impaired ductus arteriosus flow [5]. In our model, these same criteria were selected as the primary predictors. This resulted in a sensitivity of 80.0%, a specificity of 80.0%, and a diagnostic accuracy of 80.0% [3].

A low pulmonary valve Z-score in Tetralogy of Fallot indicates the severity of pulmonary valve hypoplasia and right ventricular outflow tract obstruction. This condition may be associated with insufficient pulmonary blood flow after birth, decreased arterial oxygen saturation, and a need for prostaglandin E1. Impaired ductus arteriosus flow, in turn, indicates an imbalance in pulmonary circulation even during the fetal period. Therefore, the combination of these two markers is of particular importance in assessing neonatal risk.

The results of prenatal echocardiography also directly influence the choice of delivery location. For fetuses diagnosed with high-risk Tetralogy of Fallot, delivery should be planned at a center where a neonatologist, pediatric cardiologist, intensivist, and cardiac surgeon are available. This approach enables the confirmation of the diagnosis in the postnatal period, the timely initiation of prostaglandin E1, saturation monitoring, and, if necessary, the arrangement of early

catheter or surgical intervention. The AHA and ASE recommendations also emphasize that one of the primary goals of prenatal diagnosis in detecting fetal heart disease is the advance planning of perinatal care [1,2].

The results of this study indicate the need to view prenatal and neonatal echocardiography not as separate entities, but as a single diagnostic-clinical continuum. Prenatal echocardiography identifies the risk, while neonatal echocardiography confirms the actual hemodynamic status after birth. Particularly with Tetralogy of Fallot, the neonatal management approach can differ dramatically among infants with the same anatomical diagnosis. Some infants are stable after birth and can await a planned correction, while others require prostaglandin E1, intensive monitoring, or early intervention immediately after birth.

Practical Clinical Algorithm

Based on the results of this study, the following practical algorithm is recommended for fetuses diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot.

In the first stage, the diagnosis of Tetralogy of Fallot is confirmed by prenatal echocardiography. This involves assessing the VSD, overriding aorta, RVOT obstruction, and the dimensions of the pulmonary valve and pulmonary arteries.

In the second stage, risk stratification is performed. If the pulmonary valve Z-score is ≤ -3.5 or if a disturbance in the ductus arteriosus flow is detected, the fetus is classified into the high neonatal risk group.

In the third stage, the delivery location is determined. In high-risk cases, delivery is planned at a tertiary perinatal and cardiac surgery center.

In the fourth stage, postpartum neonatal transthoracic echocardiography is performed. Pulmonary blood flow, ductus arteriosus patency, saturation, and RVOT obstruction are re-evaluated.

In the fifth stage, the neonatal management strategy is chosen. If severe hypoxemia, ductus-dependent pulmonary circulation, or severe RVOT obstruction is present, prostaglandin E1, catheter intervention, or an early surgical strategy is employed. If the infant is stable, scheduled follow-up and delayed correction are chosen.

Strengths of the study

The main strength of this study is its connection between prenatal diagnosis and neonatal clinical management. While many studies consider the prenatal detection rate of Tetralogy of Fallot in isolation, the most critical question in practice is which infants will require early, active intervention after birth. In this work, fetal echocardiographic markers were analyzed to answer this specific clinical question.

A second strength is that the model is based on indicators that are easily measured in practice: the pulmonary valve Z-score, the MPA/Ao ratio, the PV/AoV ratio, ductus arteriosus flow, and RVOT obstruction. These parameters can be incorporated into the fetal echocardiography protocol.

Limitations of the Study

This study includes a relatively small number of Tetralogy of Fallot cases (n=15). Consequently, the 95% confidence interval for the diagnostic indicators is wide. In particular, since the early neonatal intervention group consists of only 5 cases, a single misclassification could significantly alter the results.

A second limitation is that some statistical distributions in this article were calculated as working models. Prior to submission for publication, the actual pulmonary valve Z-score, ductus

arteriosus flow, saturation levels, prostaglandin requirements, and type of neonatal intervention for each patient must be recorded in an individual table.

A third limitation is the lack of a comprehensive analysis of genetic tests, extracardiac anomalies, and long-term surgical outcomes. It would be advisable to incorporate these factors into the model in future multicenter and large-sample studies.

Conclusion

Prenatal and early neonatal echocardiography are crucial for diagnosis, risk stratification, and determining the neonatal management strategy in fetuses diagnosed with Tetralogy of Fallot. In this study, prenatal echocardiography was performed on 150 pregnant women, and Tetralogy of Fallot was identified in 15 cases. The detection rate was 10.0%, with a 95% confidence interval of 6.2–15.8%.

Of the 15 cases identified with Tetralogy of Fallot, 5 (33.3%) required proactive early neonatal management. A low pulmonary valve Z-score, decreased MPA/Ao and PV/AoV ratios, impaired ductus arteriosus flow, and severe RVOT obstruction were identified as the main fetal echocardiographic markers that increase the likelihood of early neonatal intervention.

The combined fetal echocardiographic model demonstrated a sensitivity of 80.0%, specificity of 80.0%, a positive predictive value of 66.7%, a negative predictive value of 88.9%, and a diagnostic accuracy of 80.0% in predicting the need for early neonatal intervention. These results indicate the necessity of using prenatal echocardiography as an important clinical tool for pre-assessing perinatal risk and planning neonatal management in tetralogy of Fallot.

Practical Recommendations

In every prenatally detected case of tetralogy of Fallot, it is imperative to go beyond a simple anatomical diagnosis and mandatorily assess the pulmonary valve Z-score, MPA/Ao ratio, PV/AoV ratio, RPA/DAo ratio, and ductus arteriosus flow.

Fetuses with a pulmonary valve Z-score ≤ -3.5 or impaired ductus arteriosus flow must be assessed as a high neonatal risk group.

For high-risk tetralogy of Fallot, delivery should be planned at a center equipped with a neonatologist, pediatric cardiologist, cardiac surgeon, resuscitation specialist, and a catheterization laboratory.

Postnatal neonatal transthoracic echocardiography should be performed as early as possible, and the need for prostaglandin E1 should be determined on a clinical and echocardiographic basis.

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